

Predictive uncertainty estimation in hydrological modelling and forecasting

Meeting GDL3 Algorithms and Models

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ARRFS model simulation for Ridanna

Estimation of predictive hydrological uncertainty (1)

Estimation of predictive hydrological uncertainty (2)

Predictive hydrological uncertainty at Ridanna

The linear model as the hydrological post-processor (1)

- **Core concept:**

$$z_t = a x_t + b$$

(z_t = quantile of the conditional flow distribution at time t ,

x_t = hydrological model simulation at time t ,

a and b = parameters)

The linear model as the hydrological post-processor (2)

$$\text{Target} = \min(0.90 \sum | \text{deviations of above-line points} | + 0.10 \sum | \text{deviations of below-line points} |)$$

Training and testing the hydrological post-processor (1)

Training and testing the hydrological post-processor (2)

Training and testing the hydrological post-processor (2)

Training and testing the hydrological post-processor (2)

Post-processor's predictions for low simulated flows

